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Comparative Analysis between Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Technology for Teaching and Research Activities among Public University Lecturers in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education is reshaping teaching and research methodologies. This study examines the level of awareness, utilization, and AI adoption among lecturers in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from a representative sample of 525 lecturers across the selected institutions. Four research questions and two hypotheses were answered and tested at 0.05 level of significance respectively. Findings reveal a moderate to high utilization of AI tools for teaching and research, with ChatGPT (86.9%), Canvas (72.0%), and plagiarism checkers (62.1%) being the most frequently used for instructional purposes, while ChatGPT (86.7%), Canvas (75.2%), and Suite Assistant (66.7%) were prominent in research activities. Regression analysis established a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization for teaching ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 3.620$, $p < 0.05$) and research ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that increased awareness promotes higher AI adoption. The study recommend among others that the university management should procure the necessary digital resources to support seamless AI integration into teaching and research; and organize regular AI training workshops and professional development programs to improve lecturers' competence in AI adoption.

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Keyword: Artificial Intelligence, Awareness, AI Utilization, University Lecturers, Teaching, Research,

Introduction

Technological innovations, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI), have rapidly transformed various sectors, including education. The impact of emerging technologies on teaching, learning, and research in higher education institutions worldwide cannot be overstated. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education has significantly transformed teaching, research, and administrative processes globally. AI is referred to machines or software systems that is designed to perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence, has revolutionized how institutions approach pedagogy, curriculum delivery, and academic research. Its application spans across diverse domains, including data analysis, personalized learning, grading automation, and academic research management (Davenport, Guha, Grewal, & Bressgott, 2020). Through adaptive learning technologies and AI-driven platforms, students can benefit from personalized learning experiences tailored to their individual needs, learning speeds, and preferences. AI-powered systems can assist lecturers in managing classroom activities, grading assignments, and evaluating students' progress in real-time.

In the global context, AI is increasingly seen as a critical tool for improving efficiency, reducing human error, and promoting productivity in higher education settings. AI-powered tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading software, plagiarism detection tools, and AI-driven research assistants have enhanced academic workflows, making education more efficient and research more innovative (Bond, Zawacki-Richter & Marin, 2021; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). In addition, AI has shown immense potential for research management, helping academics identify trends, conduct literature reviews, analyze complex data sets, and automate administrative tasks, thereby freeing up more time for creative and intellectual pursuits (Ibrahim & Oladimeji, 2023). These innovations have fostered an environment where teaching and research productivity are maximized, and contribute to the overall enhancement of higher education outcomes. Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022) further averred that integration of AI into higher education institutions in the developed countries has resulted in notable improvements in teaching, learning, and research activities.

However, Ogunleye and Falade (2023) affirmed that factors such as institutional policies, infrastructural deficits and level of awareness among lecturers regarding

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emerging technologies has affected the adoption of AI in various institutions of learning in the developing nations of the world , especially, Nigeria. These challenges has affected the level of AI adoption in most universities in Nigeria for pedagogic experiences. The implication is that despite technological advancements, the adoption and integration of AI in higher education institutions in developing countries, such as Nigeria, have been relatively slow. While AI technologies have proven to be beneficial in various educational settings, the pace of their implementation in Nigerian universities remains sluggish, primarily due to several barriers. There are knowledge gaps in terms of awareness of potentials of AI and its adoption for teaching and research, as well as lack of professional development programmes and insufficient inclusion of AI training in university curricula might be some of the key factors hindering their adoption (Sharma, Banerjee & Mukherjee, 2021); which might account for the reasons why university lecturers are hesitant to embrace these technologies in their teaching and research practices.

Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022) and Ogunleye and Falade (2023) further reiterated that the adoption of AI technologies is closely linked to factors such as institutional support, faculty readiness, and student engagement. Understanding the barriers to AI integration in Nigerian universities is critical for fostering a more inclusive and innovative educational environment. It is evident from the literature that AI has revolutionize higher education in the developing countries; and successful integration hinges on addressing the challenges facing its implementation in various universities in Nigeria (Bello, Umar & Abdullahi, 2023). AI holds the potential to not only to enhance teaching and learning, but also to provide solutions to some of the systemic challenges facing Nigerian higher education, such as overcrowded classrooms, inefficient grading systems, and limited access to quality learning resources (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023).

Several empirical studies explored have substantiated the relationship between lecturers' awareness of information and communication technologies, however not on the domain of emerging technologies and utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for teaching and research within Nigerian universities. Broader studies provide valuable insights into this correlation, however, specific research focusing exclusively on South-west Nigeria is limited. A study conducted by Ogunfowora, Akinrinade and Ajiboye (2022) on lecturers' awareness of AI and its relationship with their digital competence.

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The findings indicated a moderate level of AI awareness among lecturers and a positive correlation between AI awareness and digital competence. The study recommended targeted training programs to enhance AI literacy and equip lecturers with essential skills for effective AI integration in teaching activities.

Similarly, Fasola (2024) and Akinyemi and Adigun (2022) examined the awareness, perception, and utilization of AI tools among Library and Information Science (LIS) lecturers in Nigerian higher institutions. The study revealed a high degree of awareness and a positive perception towards AI tools, with commonly used applications including ChatGPT, Socrative, ChatPDF, Turnitin, and Gamma. Despite recognizing AI's potential benefits, actual usage was limited due to challenges such as rapid technological advancements, lack of infrastructure, and resistance to change. Olatunde-Aiyedun and Hama (2023) assessed the proficiency levels of university lecturers in Nigeria regarding the use of AI features in presentation of software tools like MS PowerPoint, Canva, and Gamma. The study highlighted gaps in lecturers' proficiency and recommended targeted training programs to improve their skills, thereby enhancing teaching quality and student engagement. While these studies provide a general understanding of AI awareness and utilization among Nigerian university lecturers, there is a paucity of research specifically focusing on South-West Nigeria. Given the region's status as an educational hub, further empirical research is needed to assess the unique challenges and opportunities faced by lecturers in South-West Nigerian universities regarding AI integration in teaching and research.

The existing empirical literature suggests a positive correlation between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI in teaching and research. However, actual usage is often hindered by challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, rapid technological changes, and resistance to adoption. Addressing these issues through targeted training programs and enhanced AI literacy initiatives is crucial for effective AI integration in Nigerian higher education. In the context of Southwest Nigerian universities, this study seeks to explore the level of awareness among lecturers regarding AI technologies and how this awareness correlates with their utilization of AI in teaching and research activities. By investigating these relationships, the study aims to uncover the underlying factors that either facilitate or hinder AI adoption. Specifically, the research will examine lecturers' awareness and how it correlates with its utilization.

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Statement of the Research Problem

Despite AI's widespread acceptance in the educational systems of developed countries, Nigerian universities lecturers seemed to lag in integrating AI for academic purposes (Oke & Olaleye, 2023). The slow adoption of AI is presumptuously due to related factors like low awareness of the technology, inadequate procuring of infrastructure facilities, and insufficient professional training for academic staff (Onwuagboke, Nnajieta, Nzeako & Umune, 2024). AI has demonstrated its potential to optimize admission processes, enhance research productivity, and support personalized learning, yet many Nigerian institutions continue to rely on traditional methods that hinder academic progress (Adebayo, Adewale & Jimoh, 2022). As the global academic community increasingly adopts AI-driven innovations, the need for Nigerian universities to adopt emerging technologies has become more urgent. However, the awareness and perception of AI remain under-researched, limiting its utilization for teaching and research purposes (Okolo, Aruleba & Obaido, 2023). This gap in knowledge and application of AI technologies is a barrier to improving the quality and global competitiveness of Nigerian universities. This study therefore seeks to investigate the awareness of AI among university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria and how these factors correlate with the use of AI in teaching and research.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate comparative analysis between awareness and utilization of artificial intelligence technology for teaching and research activities among public university lecturers in South-west, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
2. Investigate university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
3. Examine university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
4. Investigate university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
5. Examine the relationship between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI for teaching in Southwest Nigerian universities.

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6. Examine the relationship between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI for research in Southwest Nigerian universities.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
2. What is the level of university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
3. What is the university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
4. What is the university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and the utilization of AI for teaching and research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and the utilization of AI for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.

Methodology

Population and Sampling Techniques

This study employs a descriptive research design of the cross-sectional survey type. The population comprised of all university lecturers in the public universities in Southwest Nigeria. The study focuses on six public universities in Southwest Nigeria, comprising three federal and three state-owned universities. The sampled Federal and State owned universities that participated in the study are: Lagos State {164(31.2%)}; Oyo State {193 (36.8%)} and Osun State {168(32.0%)}. A total of 525 lecturers were randomly sampled to capture a representative sample. These universities were selected based on their year of establishment and geographical distribution in the region.

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Instrumentation

A researcher-designed questionnaire titled “Awareness of AI as Correlate to Utilization” (AAICUQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire consists of three sections: Section A contained demographic information based on the university ownership, gender, faculty, department, and area of specialization; Section B contained seven items on lecturers’ awareness of AI for teaching, and Section C contained also seven items on lecturers’ awareness of AI for research. The responses were measured using a 3-point scale: Aware (3), Partially Aware (2), Not Aware (1). The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.91 the average mean score, indicating high reliability index.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistical tools used were frequency counts, percentages, and means to answer the study’s research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tools was employed to test the relationship between lecturers’ awareness and their utilization of AI for teaching and research.

Research Question 1: What is the level of university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for teaching in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 1: Level of University Lecturers’ Awareness of Emerging Technologies (AI) for Teaching

No	Items on Teaching	Fully Aware (FA) %	Slightly Aware (SA) %	Not Aware (NA) %	Mean	SD
1	Research Rabbit	37.1	29.9	33.0	2.04	0.84
2	Chat PDF	54.9	27.4	17.7	2.37	0.77
3	Consensus AI	39.2	35.2	25.5	2.14	0.79
4	Education Co-pilot	35.2	32.8	32.0	2.03	0.82
5	Scispace	27.0	37.1	35.8	1.91	0.79
6	Semantic AI	35.0	32.0	33.0	2.02	0.83
7	Elicit AI	28.8	32.2	39.0	1.90	0.82

Mean Aggregate = 2.06, SD = 0.16

The results in Table 1 shows that the level of awareness of AI for teaching among lecturers. The analysed data revealed the mean scores for lecturers’ level of awareness of these AI technologies: Research Rabbit (2.04), Chat PDF (2.37), Consensus AI (2.14),

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Education Co-pilot (2.03), Scispace (1.91), Semantic AI (2.02) and Elicit AI (1.90) for teaching. The mean score was on average with mean aggregate value of 2.06, which was moderate based on the benchmark value of 2.0. This indicates that the level of awareness of AI technologies for teaching was moderate among the sampled university lecturers.

Research Question 2: What is the level of university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of University Lecturers’ Awareness of Emerging Technologies (AI) for Research

No	Items on Research	Fully Aware (FA) %	Slightly Aware (SA) %	Not Aware (NA) %	Mean	SD
1	Suite Assistant	39.4	27.8	32.8	2.07	0.85
2	Chat	64.2	27.2	8.6	2.56	0.65
3	Copy AI	37.1	33.7	29.1	2.08	0.81
4	Sendstep AI	26.9	36.4	36.8	1.90	0.79
5	Canvas	43.4	35.4	21.1	2.22	0.77
6	Plagiarism Checkers	66.5	23.0	10.5	2.56	0.68
7	Gradescope	30.9	33.1	36.0	1.95	0.82

Mean Aggregate = 2.19, SD = 0.27

The results in Table 2 shows the level of awareness of AI for research among the university lecturers. The analysed data revealed the mean scores for lecturers’ level of awareness of these AI technologies: Suite Assistant (2.07), Chat (2.56), Copy AI (2.08), Sendstep AI (1.90), Canvas (2.22), Plagiarism Checkers (2.56) and Gradescope (1.95) for research related undertakings. The mean score was on average with mean aggregate value of 2.19, which was moderate based on the benchmark value of 2.0. This indicates that the level of awareness of AI technologies for research was moderate among the sampled lecturers. The mean aggregate of 2.19 indicates a high level of awareness among lecturers for AI tools used in research.

Research Question 3: What is the level of utilizing the available AI for teaching by lecturers in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 3: Level of utilizing the available AI for Teaching by lecturers in public universities in south-west Nigeria

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S/N	Items on Teaching	FU	%	OU	%	ΣU	%	NU	%	X	SD
8	Elicit AI	150	28.6	192	36.6	342	65.9	183	34.9	1.94	.795
9	Suite Assistant	148	28.2	205	39.0	353	67.2	172	32.8	1.95	.780
10	Copy AI	164	31.2	172	32.8	336	64.0	189	36.0	1.95	.819
11	Sendstep AI	120	22.9	194	37.0	314	59.8	211	40.2	1.83	.776
12	Canvas	181	34.5	197	37.5	378	72.0	147	28.0	2.06	.789
13	ChatGPT	288	54.9	168	32.0	456	86.9	69	13.1	2.42	.712
14	Plagiarism checkers	143	27.2	183	34.9	326	62.1	199	37.9	1.89	.801

Key: Frequently Utilised (FU), Occasionally Utilised (OU), Never Utilised (NU), Sum of Utilization (ΣU)

Mean aggregate = 2.01 SD = 0.20

Table 3 revealed lecturers' responses on the level of utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities. The collapse of responses on FU and OU (ΣU) shows level of utilizing the available AI tools: Elicit AI {342(65.9%)}; Suite Assistant {353(67.2%)}; Copy AI {336(64.0%)}; Sendstep AI {314(59.8%)}; Canvas {378(72.0%)}; ChatGPT {456(86.9%)}; and Plagiarism checkers {326(62.1%)}. The high frequency counts and percentages (ranging between 59.8% and 86.9%.) of the respondents utilizing the available AI technologies exemplified high frequency of using those emerging technologies (AI) in facilitating pedagogic experiences in the sampled universities. The mean aggregate 2.01 which is above the mean bench mark (2.0) affirms to utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for teaching by lecturers in public universities.

Research Question 4: What is the extent of using available AI tools for research by Lecturers in public universities in South-West Nigeria?

Table 4: Utilization of AI Tools for Research by Lecturers in Public Universities in South-West Nigeria

S/N	Items on Research	FU	%	OU	%	ΣU	%	NU	%	X	SD
8	Elicit AI	160	30.2	185	34.9	345	65.7	180	34.3	.92	0.810
9	Suite Assistant	150	8.4	200	38.2	350	66.7	175	33.3	.93	.790
10	Copy AI	170	2.4	170	32.2	340	64.8	185	35.2	.94	0.830
11	Sendstep AI	130	4.6	190	36.2	320	61.0	210	39.0	.85	0.780
12	Canvas	190	5.9	195	37.2	395	75.2	130	24.8	.05	0.800
13	ChapGPT	280	2.8	175	33.3	455	86.7	70	13.7	.38	0.725
14	Plagiarism Checkers	150	8.3	185	35.1	335	63.8	190	36.2	.87	0.815

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Key: Frequently Utilized (FU), Occasionally Utilized (OU), Never Utilized (NU) Mean Aggregate = 2.02 | SD = 0.19

Table 4 presents the responses from lecturers in public universities in South-West Nigeria regarding the level of utilization of the available AI tools for research. The table shows a broad engagement with AI tools, with Likert responses: "Frequently Utilized" (FU) and "Occasionally Utilized" (OU) {collapsed as the "Sum of Utilization" (ΣU)} and "Never Utilised" (NU). The collapse of responses on FU and OU (ΣU) shows level of utilizing the available AI tools: Elicit AI {345(65.7%)}; Suite Assistant {350(66.7%)}; Copy AI {340(64.8%)}; Sendstep AI {320(61.0%)}; Canvas {395(75.2%)}; ChatGPT {455(86.7%)}; and Plagiarism checkers {335(63.8%)}. The high frequency counts and percentages (ranging between 64.8% and 86.7%) of the respondents utilizing the available AI technologies exemplified high frequency of using those emerging technologies (AI) in facilitating research undertakings in the sampled universities. The mean aggregate 2.02 which is above the mean bench mark (2.0) affirms to utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for research related tasks and purposes by lecturers in public universities. The results confirm that lecturers are actively engaging with AI technologies (**Elicit AI, Suite Assistant, Copy AI, Sendstep AI, Canvas, ChapGPT and Plagiarism Checkers**) for research related purposes.

Hypotheses Testing

H01: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and utilization of AI for teaching in South-west Nigeria.

Table 5: Relative Influence of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	-3.446	1.654		-2.083
Awareness of AI	0.176	0.049	0.161	3.620

Table 5 the shows relative influence of independent variables (awareness) on dependent variables (AI utilization and adoption for teaching and research). The analysed data revealed that awareness of AI for teaching has a significant positive influence on the utilization of AI tools ($p < 0.05$). The beta value of 0.161 indicates a positive relationship between awareness and utilization.

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H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers’ level of awareness of emerging technologies and utilization of AI for research in South-west Nigeria.

Table 6: Relationship between awareness of Emerging Technologies and Adoption of AI for Research

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Awareness of emerging technologies	0.290	0.040	0.325	7.250	

Dependent Variable: Frequency of AI adoption in research.

Table 6 shows the relationship that exists between awareness of emerging technologies and adoption of AI for research. The Table shows the beta value of 0.325 for the awareness of emerging technologies variable. The analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies and their adoption of AI for research in Southwest Nigeria ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$). This indicates that as awareness of emerging technologies increases, the frequency of AI adoption in research also rises. Given the high t-value, the relationship is statistically significant, suggesting that enhancing lecturers' awareness could promote greater AI utilization in research. This indicates that awareness has a positive predictive relationship with the adoption of AI tools. The findings suggest that the greater the awareness of emerging technologies, the more likely researchers are to adopt AI for research purposes. The results also show a statistically significant influence, with a p-value 7.250 greater than alpha value (0.05), reinforcing that awareness of emerging technologies has a meaningful impact on AI adoption in research.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings reveal a growing adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among lecturers in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. The results indicate a moderate to high level of AI utilization, particularly for teaching and research. Among the most frequently used AI tools for instructional purposes, ChatGPT (86.9%), Canvas (72.0%), and plagiarism checkers (62.1%) stood out, while ChatGPT (86.7%), Canvas (75.2%), and Suite Assistant (66.7%) were prominent in research activities. These findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the increasing reliance on AI-driven tools for content delivery, assessment, and academic writing. Prior studies have shown that AI enhances pedagogical efficiency, supports personalized learning, and streamlines academic integrity monitoring (Bond et al., 2021; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). The

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high adoption of generative AI tools like ChatGPT suggests that lecturers are leveraging these technologies for content creation, automated feedback, and knowledge enhancement (Ogunfowora, Akinrinade & Ajiboye, 2022), which is consistent with the broader trend of AI integration in education (Ogunleye & Falade, 2023).

The study further established a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization for teaching ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 3.620$, $p < 0.05$) and research ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$, $p < 0.05$), reinforcing the idea that increased awareness leads to higher adoption. This finding supports that awareness significantly impact technology adoption; and faculty members with greater exposure to AI are more likely to integrate AI-enhanced learning strategies into their instructional and research activities (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023). While the increasing use of AI tools is evident, barriers such as inadequate institutional support, ethical concerns, and limited digital infrastructure continue to hinder full-scale adoption. The challenges identified in this study align with the findings of Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022), who highlighted the infrastructural and skill-based limitations affecting AI implementation in Nigerian universities.

As AI continues to redefine higher education, institutions must prioritize structured AI training and digital literacy programs to enhance lecturers' awareness and competency. Research indicates that targeted AI workshops and institutional guidelines can bridge knowledge gaps and encourage responsible AI adoption (Afolayan, Ogunleye & Olawale, 2022; Ogunleye & Falade 2023). Furthermore, policy frameworks must address ethical concerns related to AI-generated content, particularly in academic writing and research. Studies have warned against the potential risks of over-reliance on AI in scholarly work, raising issues related to authorship, originality, and data integrity (Davenport, Guha, Grewal, & Bressgott, 2020). Given these concerns, it is essential for universities to implement clear ethical guidelines and responsible AI-use policies to maintain academic standards.

The findings also highlight the importance of external support, including government funding and private sector collaboration, to facilitate AI adoption in higher education. Similar initiatives in developed nations have accelerated AI-driven innovation through strategic investments in education technology (Olatunde-Aiyedun & Hamma, 2023). Nigerian universities can benefit from similar partnerships, enabling the integration of

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AI solutions tailored to various academic disciplines (Luckin, 2018). By improving AI infrastructure, expanding training opportunities, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023), institutions can fully leverage AI's transformative potential in teaching and research while ensuring ethical and sustainable implementation.

Conclusion

The study revealed that university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria are increasingly integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their teaching and research activities. Tools such as ChatGPT, Canvas, and plagiarism checkers were found to be the most frequently used for instructional purposes, while ChatGPT, Canvas, and Suite Assistant were dominant in research activities. The findings indicate a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization, suggesting that higher levels of awareness lead to increased adoption of AI tools in academic work. Despite this growing adoption, several challenges were identified, including inadequate digital infrastructure, limited institutional support, ethical concerns, and the absence of clear policies on AI usage. These barriers hinder the seamless integration of AI in higher education. The study emphasizes the need for structured AI training programs, institutional guidelines on ethical AI use, and increased investment in AI-compatible digital resources. The study underscores the increasing role of AI in shaping academic activities among university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria. The strong link between AI awareness and its utilization suggests that targeted interventions, such as training and policy development, can further enhance AI adoption in higher education. While lecturers have begun integrating AI tools into their teaching and research, addressing infrastructural gaps and ethical concerns remains crucial for sustainable implementation. Collaboration between universities, policymakers, and stakeholders is essential in fostering a supportive environment for AI-driven innovation in academia.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Management in various universities in Nigeria should organize regular AI training sessions, seminars and workshops to enhance lecturers' understanding and effective use of AI for teaching and research. Also, lecturers should make efforts to attend professional training programmes to expose them to hands-on experiences.

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2. Various universities in Nigeria should invest in stable internet connectivity, AI-compatible software, and necessary digital resources to support seamless AI integration.
3. AI tools such as ChatGPT, plagiarism checkers, and Canvas should be systematically incorporated into academic activities while ensuring ethical usage.
4. Universities management in Nigeria should establish guidelines on AI ethics, data privacy, and responsible usage to address concerns about academic integrity and intellectual property.
5. Partnerships with tech companies, policymakers, and funding bodies should be encouraged in fostering and supporting AI-driven research and interdisciplinary innovation.
6. The use of AI tools should be encouraged by academics to meet the unique needs of different academic disciplines, and ensuring relevance and effectiveness in diverse fields.
7. Government, institutions, and private sector stakeholders should provide financial support to enhance AI accessibility, research, and innovation in higher education.

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